

ISic1452

I.Sicily inscription 1452

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

tuff

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance

Necropolis of Bagliazzo

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8769

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Θέογνις

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284891

EDR 112121

EDCS 41300059

EDCS 64800240

PHI 175671

Bibliography

Dubois, L. 1989. Inscriptions grecques dialectales de Sicile : contribution à

l'étude du vocabulaire grec colonial. Rome. At 57 (http://www.persee.fr/doc/efr_0000-0000_1989_cat_119_1)

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika* 6. Palermo. At 75

Arena, R. 1996. Iscrizioni Greche Archaiche di Sicilia e Magna Grecia. Iscrizioni di Sicilia. I. Iscrizioni di Megara Iblea e Selinunte. Pisa. At no.15

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1963. Iscrizioni inedite e revisioni selinuntine. *Kokalos*. 9: 137-156. At 137 no.1

Brugnone, A. 2006. Note epigrafiche selinuntine. *Thalassa*. 3: 45-123. At A12 tav.2.11

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1452. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4354068>